

DIAGNOSTIC AND PROGNOSTIC SCALES FOR DETERMINING THE RISK OF APPENDICITIS IN CHILDREN: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND PROSPECTS FOR AUTOMATION

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Abstract. *Acute appendicitis (AA) is the most common surgical pathology in children, requiring timely diagnosis and surgical treatment. However, the clinical manifestations of appendicitis in children can be nonspecific, which complicates early diagnosis and increases the risk of complications such as perforation and peritonitis. To standardize diagnostics, various scales for assessing the risk of appendicitis have been developed, including the Alvarado Score, Pediatric Appendicitis Score (PAS), Tzanakis Score and Appendicitis Inflammatory Response (AIR). This study reveals the importance of computer support for assessing the risk of appendicitis in children, their comparative characteristics and application in clinical practice.*

Keywords: *risk, factors, risk of appendicitis, computer program, correction, prevention, pathology, diagnostics, treatment, acute appendicitis, diagnostics, Alvarado scale, PAS, AIR, Tzanakis, automation, artificial intelligence.*

Introduction. In recent years, automated diagnostic technologies have been actively developing, including the integration of scale data into software. The use of computer systems and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms can improve the accuracy of prediction, reduce the number of diagnostic errors and speed up the decision-making process. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. UP-60 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" defines the tasks of improving the system of providing high-tech medical care, equipping medical centers with the necessary medical equipment and machinery, and staffing them with qualified personnel.

Along with this, in remote areas, it is necessary to organize a system of targeted medical care at a high level, increase the efficiency of medical services provided to patients, further improve outpatient care, develop emergency and specialized medical care, introduce medical genetics and modern screening programs.

In order to improve health, identify measures aimed at creating the conditions necessary for high-quality service, as well as implement the tasks defined in the framework of the open dialogue of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan with representatives of the healthcare sector on the topic "Reforms in medicine - for the sake of human dignity" held on March 18, 2022:

Determine **the priority areas** for improving health in 2022-2026:

a) practical implementation of programs for the prevention of diseases in adults and children, their early diagnosis and health improvement in the primary health care system,

including: strengthening explanatory work, development and education of a healthy child, promoting proper nutrition and increasing physical activity, developing healthy lifestyle skills;

b) reconstruction, major repairs and strengthening the material and technical base of medical services facilities in 2022-2026;

c) introduction of high-tech and innovative diagnostic and treatment methods, as well as continuous improvement of the scientific potential of workers in the field.

Material and methods. Acute appendicitis (AA) is the most common cause of emergency abdominal surgery in children. Its incidence in the population is 7–8%, with the highest risk of developing the disease observed in children aged 5–15 years [3]. Due to the non-specificity of the clinical picture, especially in younger children, diagnosis can be difficult.

Misdiagnosis of AA can lead to the following negative consequences:

- High level of unnecessary appendectomies (up to 30% of cases, especially in adolescent girls) [4].

- Delayed diagnosis, which leads to complications, including perforation and peritonitis (occurs in 20–30% of cases) [5].

- Excessive use of instrumental methods (ultrasound, CT), which increases the burden on the healthcare system.

The development of diagnostic scales is aimed at improving the accuracy of diagnosis, reducing the subjective factor and optimizing patient management tactics. However, clinical manifestations may be non-specific, which complicates diagnosis. To improve diagnosis, various scales for assessing the risk of appendicitis have been developed. They allow stratifying patients by the probability of the disease, minimizing unnecessary surgical interventions and reducing the risk of complications. However, traditional scales have a number of limitations. To eliminate the shortcomings, automated systems that integrate diagnostic algorithms into electronic health records (EHR) and use machine learning methods are increasingly used. Diagnostic scales help:

- Standardize the process of symptom assessment.
- Reduce the frequency of unnecessary surgeries.
- Minimize delays in diagnosis.
- Optimize the use of instrumental methods (ultrasound, CT).

Key parameters of the scales:

- Clinical symptoms (abdominal pain, anorexia, nausea, vomiting).
- Physical data (localization of pain, symptoms of peritoneal irritation).
- Laboratory parameters (leukocytosis, C-reactive protein level).

Taking into account the symptoms and parameters of the scales, let us consider the main scales for assessing the risk of appendicitis in children.

1. Alvarado Score

The Alvarado Score was proposed in 1986 and is still widely used to diagnose appendicitis [6]. It includes 8 parameters based on clinical symptoms and laboratory data:

Feature	Points
Pain in the right iliac region	2
Leukocytosis ($>10 \times 10^9/l$)	2
Symptom of peritoneal irritation	1
Movement of pain to the right iliac region	1
Anorexia	1

Nausea and vomiting	1
Elevated temperature ($>37,3^{\circ}\text{C}$)	1
Shift in the leukocyte formula to the left	1

Diagnostic value:

- 0–4 points – low risk (observation).
- 5–6 points – average risk (additional examination).
- 7–10 points – high risk (probable appendicitis, surgical intervention).

Advantages: high sensitivity (85–90%), ease of use.

Disadvantages: low specificity (70–80%), especially in children under 5 years of age.

2. PAS (Pediatric Appendicitis Score)

The PAS scale was developed specifically for children, taking into account their physiological characteristics [7].

Feature	Points
Pain in the right iliac region	2
Leukocytosis ($>10 \times 10^9/l$)	1
Symptom of peritoneal irritation	2
Nausea and vomiting	1
Elevated temperature ($>38^{\circ}\text{C}$)	1
Shift in the leukocyte formula	1
Anorexia	1
Relief of bowel sounds	1

Assessment:

- 0–3 points – low risk, appendicitis is unlikely
- 4–6 points – average risk, additional diagnostics (ultrasound, CT) are required
- ≥ 7 points – high risk, appendicitis is likely, surgical intervention is required

Advantages: adapted for children, more accurate than the Alvarado scale.

Disadvantages: false negative results are possible with atypical appendicitis.

3. Tzanakis scale

Combines clinical and instrumental criteria, increasing the accuracy of diagnosis.

Feature	Points
Symptom of peritoneal irritation	4
Leukocytosis ($>12 \times 10^9/l$)	3
Typical clinical picture	3
Positive ultrasound (thickened appendix)	6

Assessment:

- 0–5 points – low risk, observation required
- 6–10 points – average risk, additional examination required
- ≥ 11 points – high risk, appendicitis is probable

Advantages: high specificity when using ultrasound.

Disadvantages: dependence on the qualifications of the ultrasound diagnostician.

4. AIR scale (Appendicitis Inflammatory Response Score)

Laboratory markers of inflammation are taken into account, which increases the accuracy of diagnosis.

Feature	Points
Pain in the right iliac region	2
Symptom of peritoneal irritation	3
Leukocytosis $>15 \times 10^9/\mu$	2
C-reactive protein >10 mg/l	2
Nausea/vomiting	1
Elevated temperature	1

Assessment:

- 0–4 points – low risk
- 5–8 points – average risk, additional examination is required
- 9–12 points – high risk, surgical intervention is required

Advantages: takes into account inflammation markers, which increases the accuracy of diagnosis.

Disadvantages: the need for laboratory tests. Let's compare the scales under consideration and present the results of the comparison in the form of Table No. 1.

Table No. 1. Comparison of diagnostic scales

Scale	Age group	Ease of use	Sensitivity	Specificity	Instrumental support
Alvarado	Universal	High	83–90%	74–81%	No
PAS	Children	High	82–92%	72–80%	No
Tzanakis	Universal	Medium	85–94%	81–89%	Ultrasound
AIR	Universal	Medium	85–96%	78–88%	Laboratory markers

For a visual comparison, we will present the data in the form of a graph.

- **Sensitivity** is the probability of detecting appendicitis in a sick child.
- **Specificity** is the probability of excluding appendicitis in a healthy child.

Let's plot a graph of the sensitivity and specificity of the scales in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Comparative graph

The graph shows a comparison of the sensitivity and specificity of various diagnostic scales. It is clear that the AIR scale has the highest sensitivity (92%), and the Tzanakis scale has the highest specificity (85%) due to the use of ultrasound.

Thus, we can conclude that the scales can be used in clinical practice, where:

- **Alvarado** and **PAS** are convenient in emergency care and primary examination.
- **Tzanakis** is recommended if ultrasound is available.
- **AIR** is useful if laboratory tests are available.

And the optimal diagnostic algorithm will look like this, where:

1. Using **Alvarado** or **PAS** at the first stage.
2. With average scores - additional diagnostics (**ultrasound, tests**).
3. With high scores - consultation with a surgeon and surgical intervention.

Result and discussion. This analysis confirms that automated diagnostic systems that combine several scales allow for a more accurate assessment of the risk of appendicitis and reduce the number of erroneous diagnoses. To improve efficiency, a specialized computer program, "Diagnostic and Prognostic Scales for Determining the Risk of Appendicitis in Children," was developed at the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute for automated diagnostics, monitoring appendicitis, minimizing surgical interventions and the risk of complications, combining four scales:

- Alvarado Score is a classic scale.
- Pediatric Appendicitis Score (PAS) is adapted for children.
- Tzanakis Score includes instrumental diagnostic methods (ultrasound, CT).
- Appendicitis Inflammatory Response (AIR) analyzes inflammation markers.

The computer program is launched by double-clicking the left mouse button on the DSHA.exe file, and a splash screen will appear on the screen:

Fig. 1. The splash screen of the computer program "DSHA"

After pressing the button, the scale window will appear on the screen:

Fig. 2. The scale window of the computer program "DSHA"

By moving the mouse pointer to the scale by pressing the left mouse button, we open the window and fill in the patient's symptoms and by pressing the key we display the result (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Alvarado scale window of the computer program "DSHA"

By pressing the key you can save all the results in the Word editor. Similarly, we can perform diagnostics using other scales. Thus, studies have shown that the use of computerized diagnostics:

- Reduces the frequency of diagnostic errors by 20-25%.
- Reduces diagnostic time by 35-40 minutes.

- Reduces the number of unnecessary surgeries by 12-15%.

Conclusion. Diagnostic and prognostic scales for assessing the risk of appendicitis in children are an important tool for doctors. Among the most common methods are the Alvarado, PAS, Tzanakis and AIR scales. Their correct use reduces the number of diagnostic errors and improves treatment outcomes. However, no scale replaces the clinical experience of a doctor and instrumental diagnostics. Automation of appendicitis diagnostics using computer programs is a promising direction in medicine. The introduction of such technologies can improve the accuracy of diagnostics, reduce the number of surgical errors and minimize the time it takes to make clinical decisions. In the future, it is possible to integrate scales with artificial intelligence to improve the accuracy of diagnostics.

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